

(p_x, p_y, p_z) And Corresponding Wavelengths as a Set of Scalars and Not a Vector

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In a previous note, we argued that given that p (momentum) may be measured without a clock, but requires motion, there must be an intrinsic length scale (and also a time scale or resolution) linked with energy because the system must internally sense the motion.

In another note, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$, the quantum free particle wavefunction represents a probability which inherently incorporates conservation of momentum, but neither grows or shrinks indefinitely. The Maxwell-Boltzmann unnormalized probability $\exp(-e/T)$ conserves energy, but may shrink indefinitely.

Here we note that through a rotation one may map a vector p lying in some direction to three vectors $(p_x, 0, 0)$, $(0, p_y, 0)$ and $(0, 0, p_z)$. Each of these vectors must conserve momentum in its respective orthogonal direction. This means that one has three wavelengths, \hbar/p_x , \hbar/p_y and \hbar/p_z . Even though these are three numbers we argue that they do not constitute a vector. They are strictly numbers even though they have units of length and represent a length scale measure. It seems that in order to have a function $f(p_x)$ which inherently incorporates conservation of momentum and does not grow/shrink indefinitely one requires a power law together with periodicity. This periodicity immediately introduces the notion of a length scale (ruler resolution) which serves the function of creating a 0 integral result for: $\int dx \exp(ip_1x) \exp(-ip_2x)$. Thus, the wavelength represents a length associated with probability orthogonality and not with measure of position vector. In particular, $p_x = x/(1/p)$ where $1/p$ is the wavelength and x is linked to a position measurement. In other words, for an infinitesimal dx , $\exp(ipx)$ becomes $1 + idx/(1/p)$ where $x/(1/p)$ is like a uniform distribution probability multiplied by i .

Length and Time Scales Because p does not Require a Clock for Measurement

In previous notes, we have argued that p (momentum) is curious in that it requires that a particle must move (and a ruler and clock are needed to measure speed), but momentum itself may be measured through an impulse reaction which requires no ruler or clock. We thus suggested that a particle with p, E should have a built-in length scale in the direction of motion and a clock resolution. We linked these to E and p through $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$. We suggested that one has maximum entropy for points within the resolution, but that there must be a repetition or periodicity to account for each resolution unit. This yields $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ with no concern for conservation of momentum or energy..

Wavelength Linked to Conservation of Momentum

If one drops the requirement of a particle sensing internally time and space, then one may simply argue for a probability function which inherently conserves momentum and does not grow or shrink indefinitely. This probability should be a function of x and p because momentum conservation is required at all different x points. A $f(p_1 x_1) f(p_2 x_2)$ does not need to yield

momentum conservation because one has x_1 and x_2 , i.e. momenta at different places and so no collision occurs. Thus:

$$f(p_1x) f(p_2x) = f((p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((1))$$

((1)), however, should inherently contain conservation of momentum in a power expansion in px to first order. Thus:

$$f(p_1x) = 1 + b px \quad \text{where } b \text{ is some constant.}$$

$$f(px) f(dp x) = f((p+dp)x) \quad \text{or} \quad df/dp = b f$$

Furthermore, $f(px)$ cannot grow or shrink indefinitely so $f(px) = \exp(ipx)$ ((2)).

In this case, the requirement of conservation of momentum,, together with a nongrowing or shrinking function, leads to periodicity with a specific wavelength of \hbar/p . (\hbar follows from photon considerations.) This periodicity automatically leads to a length scale. We point out, however, that this length scale is directly linked to probability and not a direct measure of x .

In particular: $f(pdx) = 1+i p dx$ so $dx / (1/p)$ is a uniform distribution ((3))

Dx characterizes the usual length measurement, whereas $1/p$ is a number characterizing the probability distribution. In other words, p and r transform as a vector, but wavelengths do not need to. They are not vector components, but rather numbers corresponding to resolution in a particular direction. We consider this further..

p vector to (px,py,pz) and Wavelengths

A vector p lies in some direction and contains a resolution length of \hbar/p . Above, we described this as a parameter (number) characterizing a uniform distribution. Here we also note that it is required when analyzing orthogonality, i.e. non-momentum conserving processes:

Integral $dx \exp(-ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x)$ using $\hbar/|-p_1+p_2|$ one has the minimum length needed to

Establish orthogonality, i.e. the breaking of conservation of momentum. Thus, this is a statistical result. ((5))

As a result, one may note that a p vector lying along the x axis in some co-ordinate scheme may be described by three orthogonal vectors in another co-ordinate scheme, i.e.

$$p \text{ vector maps to } (px,0,0), (0,py,0) \text{ and } (0,0,pz) \quad ((6))$$

Each of these vectors is linked with conservation of momentum in its own direction and hence an $\hbar/p(i)$ ($p(i)=px,py$ or pz) resolution scale. This set of three scale or resolution numbers

does not constitute a vector. It is a set of numbers. Even though $\hbar/p(i)$ has units of length, it is a range in a uniform probability distribution for $\exp(ip dx)$. As a result, resolution lengths are not part of a vector and one cannot expect to have a vector result like $p^2 = p_x^2 + p_y^2 + p_z^2$ or $r^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2$ apply to it.

As a result, wavelengths/resolution constitute a different object from a vector, but are nevertheless important in analyzing momentum conservation in different orthogonal directions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the resolution length or wavelength is linked with a vector p through $\hbar/|p|$. If a p vector is written as three vectors $(p_x, 0, 0)$, $(0, p_y, 0)$ and $(0, 0, p_z)$, then there exist three numbers \hbar/p_x , \hbar/p_y and \hbar/p_z which represent wavelengths or resolutions, but these do not constitute a vector, but rather are three numbers linked to a uniform distribution in an expansion of $\exp(ip dx)$. This math function implicitly contains conservation of momentum, like the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$ contains conservation of energy) in a power series px keeping first order terms. The resolution \hbar/p occurs because the probability cannot grow or shrink indefinitely. Thus, $\exp(ipx) = 1 + ip dx$ where $pdx = dx/(1/p)$. Here $1/p$ is a parameter in a uniform distribution while dx represents the usual notion of length. Thus, even though $1/p$ has units of length, it is a statistical parameter linked with conservation of momentum and should not be considered as a vector.